

The Role of Background Concentrations in the Analysis of the Ecological State of Rivers of the Akhuryan Water Basin Management Area

Simonyan G.S.^{1*}, Otaryan M.M.², Simonyan A.G.³

^{1*}Assistant professor, Faculty of Chemistry, Yerevan State University, Yerevan, Armenia.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8162-9748>;

²Candidate of Economic sciences. Ijevan Branch of Yerevan State University. Ijevan, Tavush Province, Armenia.

³Candidate of technical sciences. Gayluk.am Management Service. Yerevan, Armenia.

Corresponding Author

Simonyan G.S.

Assistant professor, Faculty of Chemistry, Yerevan State University, Yerevan, Armenia.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8162-9748>;

Abstract

The article studies the water quality classes of the Akhuryan, Ashotsk, Karkachun, and Metsamor rivers for 2013-2024 based on the analysis of background concentrations of hydrochemical parameters. The analysis showed that the background concentrations of suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, chemical oxygen demand, biological oxygen demand (5-days), ammonium, nitrite, and phosphate ions, as well as the background concentrations of the following metals: manganese, molybdenum, iron, boron, and arsenic, were exceeded in the waters of the studied river. The analysis of the obtained data can be used for complex management of water resource quality assessment in communities. It was shown that the Water Framework Directive developed by the European Union played an important role in the transition of the river water quality assessment process in Armenia from the assessment of maximum permissible concentrations of hydrochemical parameters to a more comprehensive approach based on natural background concentrations. This amendment, which has been in effect since 2011, emphasizes the importance of ecological integrity and the use of natural river basins for water quality assessment. The RA Government's Resolution "On Establishing Water Quality Standards for Each River Basin

Management Area” distinguishes five separate classes, and the chemical water quality assessment is based on the class with the most unfavorable quality indicator.

Key Words: Water quality, background concentration, river. Akhuryan, Ashotsk, Karkachun, Metsamor, management, Armenia

Introduction

In Armenia, there are 400 rivers with a total length of more than 10 km. Mostly these rivers are small, fast and mountainous. The total average river flow originating within the country is 6,250 mln. m³ /year, of which 3,029 mln. m³ /year is formed from springs and underground water drainage. About 940 million m³ is formed from the border rivers Araks and Akhuryan [1].

Water resources management is based on viewing water as an integral part of the ecosystem, a natural resource, and a socioeconomic good, the quantity and quality of which determine the nature of its use. It is important to note that, within the framework of "Water Resources Management in Armenia," a water resources management model was developed for the country as a whole, based on individual river basins. This model serves as a starting point for integrated river basin-based planning and water resource management. The country has 14 large river basins. The territory of the Republic of Armenia is divided into six: Northern, Akhuryan, Hrazdan, Sevan, Ararat and Southern surface water management basins.

River environmental assessments are carried out using complex indicators that allow for a quantitative assessment of water pollution using a large number of water quality indicators simultaneously [2, 3]. It should be noted that most of the complex indicators of water body conditions developed to date are in some way related to the current maximum permissible concentrations (MPCs) [4], which were developed in the USSR and used to assess the pollution of aquatic systems. It should be noted that the shortcomings of MPCs include the lack of consideration of local characteristics, the application of the same standards for rivers flowing in different physical and geographical zones, and the failure to account for the natural background content of pollutants in aquatic systems. Background Concentration (BC) is the value of the water quality indicator concentration before exposure to any source of pollution.

According to the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) (2000/60 / EC), all European surface waters should be in good ecological condition after 2015, and water objects with poor quality water should be improved through targeted measures quality to a better status [5].

The Directive aims for "good status" for all ground and surface waters (rivers, lakes, transitional waters, and coastal waters) in the EU. The purpose of the WFD is to prevent deterioration of the

water bodies, enhance status of aquatic ecosystems, reduce pollution from priority substances, promote sustainable water use and contribute to mitigate the effects of floods and droughts [5].

The ecological and chemical status of surface waters are assessed according to the following criteria:

- Biological quality (fish, benthic invertebrates, aquatic flora)
- Hydromorphological quality such as river bank structure, river continuity or substrate of the river bed
- Physical-chemical quality such as temperature, oxygenation and nutrient conditions
- Chemical quality that refers to environmental quality standards for river basin specific pollutants. These standards specify maximum concentrations for specific water pollutants. If even one such concentration is exceeded, the water body will not be classed as having a “good ecological status”[5].

Each EU Member State has developed classroom schemes for water quality classification according to WFD.

For example, water quality assessment in the Danube River Basin according to the EU WFD is carried out according to separate indicators [6]. In this classification scheme, indicators are classified into five classes. Class I is referred to as "reference" or background concentration; class II is a target value that should be followed; the III-V classes are part of the "non-executable" classification scheme and their values are usually 2-5 times higher than the target value. Germany's chemical quality classification scheme consists of 4 main classes and 3 subclasses, with a similar biological classification. The grades obtained are mapped through color codes.

Due to the lack of hydrobiological monitoring in Armenia, assessment was made only with the use of water quality chemical indicators. Natural background concentrations of hydrochemical parameters were taken into account. The determination of background concentrations according to the EU WFD was performed using a statistical method using the probability logarithmic distribution function. The expected background status of the reference state is the absence or insignificance of anthropogenic pressure. It is closely connected with background concentration (BC).

The calculations of the BC took place in the RA rivers in 2005-2010 hydrochemical monitoring. The Government of the Republic of Armenia, "Decree N75-N of 27 January 2011", establishes the surface water quality assessment system in Armenia for each parameter of the water quality for

each water basin by the five class status: "excellent" (1st grade), "good" (2nd grade), "average" (3rd grade), "unsatisfactory" (grade 4) and "bad" (5-class). The general assessment of the chemical quality of water is shaped by the class of the lowest quality indicator [7].

If the different indicators of the quality of the surface water object fall into different classes of quality, the final classification is considered the worst. The following principle applies: "If someone is in bad shape, then everyone is in a bad condition" or "one is out, everyone is out" principle.

The advantage of the new water quality standards in Armenia is that the classification of environmental standards is based on natural biocenoses. The selection of indicators was based on the load on surface waters in the Republic of Armenia (mainly 43 parameters).

The water quality of the Hrazdan River Basin Management Area [8], of the Aghsrev and Getik rivers [9], as well as Lake Sevan and several reservoirs in Armenia [2] has been assessed using BC. This study aims to evaluate the water quality of the rivers of Akhuryan Water Basin Management Area: Akhuryan, Ashotsk, Karkachun, Metsamor, using BC.

2. Experimental

2.1 Study area

Akhuryan is a river running along the Armenian plateau in the South Caucasus. It is the left tributary of Araks. In the upper current flows through the territory of Armenia, in the lower one - along the border of Armenia with Turkey. It flows from the Arpi lich reservoir, flows into the Araks near the village of Bagaran. The river Akhuryan has length of 186 km and river basin of 9670 km². There are five sampling points on the Akhuryan River: № 31 – 0.5 km above Amasia City; № 32 – 1.0 km below Amasia City; № 33 – 1.0 km above Gyumri City; № 34 – 5.0 km below Gyumri City; № 35 – 0.5 km below Ervandashat village [1,3,10].

The river **Ashotsk** has length of 20 km and river basin of 197 km², it is the left tributary of the Akhuryan river. Two sampling points, № 36 – 0.5 km below the Artashen village and № 37 – at the mouth of the river. The river **Karkachun** has length of 55 km and river basin of 1220 km², it is the left tributary of the Akhuryan river. Sampling point, № 38 – 0.5 km below the Garibjanyan village [1,3,10].

The **Metsamor** (Sevjur) River flows from the springs of the Aragats mountain massif and flows into the Araks River. The length of the river is 40 km, the area of the basin is 1610 km². In comparison with other rivers, Armenia has one of the most stable regimes. The current of the river is very slow. The main tributary of Sevjur is the Kasaha River [1]. There are three sampling points on the Sevjur River: No. 40 - 10 km above the town of Vagarshapat, No. 41 - 11 km south-west of Vagarshapat No. 42 - 0.5 km below Ranchpar village [1.3].

2.2. Method of water quality classification

The overall assessment of the chemical quality of water is formed by the class of the lowest quality indicator. Thus, if different quality indicators of a surface water body fall into different quality classes, the final classification is considered to be the worst. According to the Government of the Republic of Armenia's decision "On the Establishment of Water Quality Standards for Each Water Basin Management District," five classes are distinguished. Each class is designated by color (see Table 1): "excellent" (1st class - blue), "good" (2nd class - green), "average" (3rd class - yellow), "unsatisfactory" (4th class - brown) and "bad" (5th class - red). The following principle is applied: "If someone is in bad shape, then everyone is in bad shape" or the principle "someone went out, everyone went out"

Table 1. Water quality classification according to the EU WFD

Water quality class	1	2	3	4	5
Water quality	Excellent	Good	Average	Unsatisfactory	Bad
Assessment					

Results and Discussion

As mentioned in the introduction to this article, until 2011, the MPC was used to assess the pollution of water systems in Armenia, which has the following shortcomings: the same criteria are applied to rivers flowing in different physical and geographical zones and do not take into account the natural background content of pollutants in the rivers.

Tables 2 and 3 present the environmental criteria for river water quality for some parameters of the Akhuryan and Metsamor river basins - MPC and BC.

As can be seen, the BCs (water quality class I) of the Akhuryan and Metsamor river basins differ from each other. This was expected, since these rivers flow through different physical and geographical zones. It also follows that the MPC differs from the BC (water quality class I) and in some cases exceeds the BC.

Table 2 - Environmental standards for the quality of river water in the Akhuryan River basin

Quality parameters	MPC	Water quality class according to BC					Units
		I	II	III	IV	V	
COD	30	10	25	40	80	>80	mgO ₂ /L
BOD ₅	3	3	5	9	18	>18	mgO ₂ /L
DO	>6	>7	>6	>5	>4	>4	mgO ₂ /L
NH ₄ ⁺	0.5	0.057	0.4	1.2	2.4	>2.4	mg/L
NO ₂ ⁻	0.08	0.007	0.06	0.12	0.3	>0.3	mgN/L
PO ₄ ⁻³	0.1	0.26	0.3	0.6	1.2	>1.2	mg/L
Suspended solids	10	25	30	60	120	>120	mg/L
Fe	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.5	1	>1	mg/L
Mn	10	26	52	104	208	>208	µg/L.
Mo	1.0	0.97	1.94	3.88	7.76	>7.76	µg/L.
B	0.5	0.18	0.45	0.7	1	>1	mg/L
As	10	0.42	10	50	100	>100	µg/L.

Table 3. Environmental standards for the quality of river water in the Metsamor River basin

Quality parameters	MPC	Water quality class according to BC					Units
		I	II	III	IV	V	
COD	30	10	25	40	80	>80	mgO ₂ /L
BOD ₅	3	3	5	9	18	>18	mgO ₂ /L

DO	>6	>7	>6	>5	>4	>4	mgO ₂ /L
NH ₄ ⁺	0.5	0.08	0.4	1.2	2.4	>2.4	mg/L
NO ₂ ⁻	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.12	0.3	>0.3	mgN/L
PO ₄ ⁻³	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.6	1.2	>1.2	mg/L
Suspended solids	10	8.1	15.3	25.5	51.0	>51.0	mg/L
Fe	0.1	0.1	0.122	0.5	1	>1	mg/L
Mn	10	23	46	92	184	>184	µg/L.
B	0.5	0.1	0.45	0.7	1	>1	mg/L
As	10	0.65	10	50	100	>100	µg/L.

Table 4 shows the water quality classes of the Akhuryan, Ashotsk, Karkachun, and Metsamor rivers for 2013-2024. The water quality data for the rivers according to BC are taken from the website “Hydrometeorology and Monitoring Center” SNCO of the Ministry of Environment of the Republic of Armenia (On the results of ecological monitoring of the environment of the Republic of Armenia. Bulletin. 2013-2024) [11].

It should be noted that the Ashotsk and Karkachun rivers are also located in the Akhuryan River basin.

In 2013, the water in the Akhuryan River upstream of Amasia was of "good" quality (2nd class), in the downstream of Amasia it was of "unsatisfactory" quality (4th class), due to phosphate ion. In the Akhuryan River upstream of Gyumri it was of "good" quality (2nd class), in the downstream of Gyumri it was of "bad" quality (5th class), due to ammonium ion and suspended particles. In the Akhuryan River downstream of Yervandashat it was of "average" quality (3rd class), due to phosphate ion. In 2014, the water in the Akhuryan River upstream of Amasia was of "good" quality (2nd class), in the downstream of Amasia it was of "unsatisfactory" quality (4th class), due to phosphate ion. The water quality of the Akhuryan River upstream of Gyumri is of “good” quality (2nd class), while the water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of Yervandashat is of “bad” quality (5th class) due to ammonium ion and suspended particles. The water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of Yervandashat is of “average” quality (3rd class) due to phosphate ion.

Table 3. Classification of Water quality of the Rivers Akhuryan, Ashotsk, Karkachun and Metsamor based on the BC

Rivers	Akhuryan					Ashotsk		Karkachun	Metsamor		
	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	40	41	42
2013	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Blue	Green	Red	Yellow	Orange	Orange
2014	Green	Orange	Green	Red	Yellow	Blue	Green	Red	Red	Red	Red
2015	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Orange	Yellow
2016	Yellow	Yellow	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Orange	Yellow
2017	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange
2018	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange
2019	Orange	Orange	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Red	Orange
2020	Red	Red	Yellow	Orange	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange
2021	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Green	Yellow	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange
2022	Red	Red	Red	Red	Orange	Green	Orange	Red	Red	Orange	Orange
2023	Green	Red	Orange	Red	Orange	Green	Orange	Red	Orange	Orange	Orange
2024	Green	Red	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Yellow

In 2015, the water quality of the Akhuryan River upstream of Amasia is of “good” quality (2nd class), while the water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of Gyumri is of “average” quality (3rd class) due to phosphate ion. The chemical quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of Gyumri is of “unsatisfactory” quality (4th class) due to ammonium ion and suspended particles. The water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of Yervandashat is of “average” quality (3rd class) due to suspended particles.

In the Ashotsk River upstream of Artashen, the water is of "good" quality (2nd class), and in the river mouth section, it is "average" (3rd class), due to COD and arsenic.

In 2016, the water in the Akhuryan River upstream and downstream of Amasia, as well as downstream of Yervandashat, is of “average” quality (3rd class). Above Amasia, due to COD,

phosphate ion, iron and suspended particles, below Amasia, due to phosphate ion, iron and suspended particles, below Yervandashat, due to COD and suspended particles, in the sections upstream and downstream of Gyumri, it is of “unsatisfactory” quality (4th class). Above Gyumri, due to iron and suspended particles, below Gyumri, due to ammonium and nitrite ions, iron and suspended particles.

And in 2017, the water in the Akhuryan River upstream and downstream of Amasia, upstream and downstream of Gyumri, was assessed as “unsatisfactory” quality (4th class). The water in the section below Yervan-Dashat was assessed as being of "average" quality (class 3).

The picture is the same in 2018 and 2019. Thus, in 2018, the water quality of the Akhuryan River in the sections above and below Amasia, below Gyumri, was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (class 4) due to iron, phosphate and nitrite ions and suspended matter. In the sections above Gyumri and below Bagaran, the water quality of the river was assessed as “average” (class 3) due to chemical oxygen demand, phosphate ion, molybdenum, manganese, iron, total phosphorus and suspended matter.

In 2019, the water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of the village of Amasia was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (class 4) due to phosphate ions, and upstream and downstream of the city of Gyumri as “average” (class 3) due to ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, molybdenum, iron, total phosphorus and suspended matter. In the downstream of the village of Bagaran, the water quality of the river was assessed as “average” (class 3) due to phosphate ions, molybdenum, manganese, iron and suspended matter.

In 2020-2022, the water quality of the Akhuryan River is deteriorating. Thus, in 2020, the water quality of the Akhuryan River downstream of the village of Amasia was assessed as “bad” (class 5) due to ammonium and phosphate ions. In the areas above Gyumri city and below Bagaran village, the water quality was assessed as "average" (class 3) due to molybdenum, manganese, iron, total phosphorus, and suspended solids. In the area below Gyumri city, the water quality was assessed as "unsatisfactory" (class 4) due to ammonium, nitrite ions, and iron.

In 2021, the water quality of the Akhuryan River in the sections below Amasia village, above Gyumri city, below Gyumri city and below Bagaran village was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (4th class). Below Amasia village, due to ammonium ion and iron, above Gyumri city, due to iron, below Gyumri city, due to ammonium, nitrite ions, iron and suspended solids, below Bagaran village, due to iron and suspended solids. And in 2022, the water quality of the Akhuryan River in

the sections below Amasia village, above and below Gyumri city was assessed as “bad” (5th class) due to phosphate ion. Below Bagaran village, the water quality was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (4th class) due to iron and suspended solids.

In 2023-2024, the water quality of the Akhuryan River in the section above the village of Amasia was assessed as “good” (2nd class), in the sections below the village of Amasia and below the city of Gyumri “bad” (5th class). In the section below the village of Amasia, due to ammonium ion, in the section below the city of Gyumri – iron and suspended solids. In the sections above the city of Gyumri and below the village of Bagaran, the water quality was assessed as “average” (3rd class). In the section above the city of Gyumri – due to ammonium ion, arsenic, molybdenum, iron and suspended solids, in the section below the village of Bagaran – arsenic, molybdenum, manganese, iron, total dissolved salts and suspended solids.

The data on the Akhuryan River shows that the water quality of the Akhuryan River is deteriorating outside the cities of Amasia and Gyumri, which can be explained by the impact of untreated or insufficiently treated domestic wastewater from the mentioned cities and unorganized runoff from the fields.

In 2013 and 2014, the water at sampling point No. 36 in the Ashotsk River upstream of Artashen was of “excellent” quality (class 1), and in the remaining years the water was of “good” quality (class 2). In the Ashotsk River estuary section in 2013 and 2014, the water at sampling point No. 37 was of “good” quality (class 2). In 2022 and 2024, it was of Unsatisfactory quality due to arsenic and boron. In the remaining years, it was of “average” quality (class 3) due to iron, arsenic and boron, suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, chemical oxygen demand, five-day biological oxygen demand

In 2013-2020, the water in the mouth of the Karkachun River was of "poor" quality (class 5), which is mainly due to suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, chemical oxygen demand, five-day biological oxygen demand, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, as well as manganese,

In 2013, the water of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat was of the 3rd class, due to COD, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions. The water southeast of Vagharshapat was of the 4th class, due to ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, and in the sections downstream of Ranchpar village the water was of “satisfactory” quality (4th class) due to COD and phosphate ions.

In the sections of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat, southeast of Vagharshapat and downstream of Ranchpar village, the water was of “poor” quality (5th class) due to ammonium and phosphate ions in the section south of Vagharshapat, and phosphate ions in the sections southeast of Vagharshapat and downstream of Ranchpar village.

In 2015, the water in the sections of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat and downstream of the village of Ranchpar is of "average" quality (3rd class). South of Vagharshapat - due to COD, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, downstream of the village of Ranchpar - due to COD, nitrite and ammonium ions, in the section southeast of Vagharshapat the water is of "unsatisfactory" quality (4th class) - due to ammonium and nitrite ions. And in 2016, the water in the Metsamor River south and southeast of Vagharshapat is of "unsatisfactory" quality (4th class). South of Vagharshapat, due to ammonium, nitrite and sulfate ions; southeast of Vagharshapat, due to dissolved oxygen, nitrite and phosphate ions; below Ranchpar village, it is of "average" quality (class 3) due to COD, nitrite and nitrate ions, manganese and boron.

In 2017, 2018, 2020, 2021 and 2023, the water quality of the Metsamor River throughout its course was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (class 4). The water quality of the Metsamor River throughout its course was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (class 4) due to chemical oxygen demand, dissolved oxygen, suspended solids, ammonium, nitrite and phosphate ions, boron and manganese. In 2019. the water quality of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat city and downstream of Ranchpar village was assessed as “unsatisfactory” (4th class) due to dissolved oxygen and ammonium ion, in the section southeast of Vagharshapat city – “bad” (5th class) due to dissolved oxygen. In 2022. the water quality of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat city was assessed as “bad” (5th class) due to ammonium ion, in the sections southeast of Vagharshapat city and downstream of Ranchpar village – “unsatisfactory” (4th class). Southeast of Vagharshapat city due to ammonium and nitrite ions, manganese, suspended solids, downstream of Ranchpar village nitrite ion and boron. And in 2024, the water quality of the Metsamor River south of Vagharshapat city and southeast of Vagharshapat city was assessed as "bad" (class 5). In the section south of Vagharshapat city, due to ammonium ion, in the section southeast of Vagharshapat city, due to dissolved oxygen and ammonium ion. In the section downstream of Ranchpar village, the water quality was assessed as "average" (class 3),

due to dissolved oxygen, chemical oxygen demand, ammonium, nitrite, phosphate ions, arsenic, manganese, iron, boron and total phosphorus.

Conclusion

It has been shown that in Armenia, based on the requirements of the EU WFD and in accordance with the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Armenia "On the Establishment of Water Quality Standards for Each River Basin Management Area," five water quality classes are distinguished. The overall assessment of chemical water quality is determined based on the class of the lowest quality indicator. Each class is color-coded: "excellent" (Class 1: blue), "good" (Class 2: green), "average" (Class 3: yellow), "unsatisfactory" (Class 4: brown), and "poor" (Class 5: red). The analysis revealed that maximum permissible concentrations of manganese, molybdenum, iron, sulfur, suspended solids, COD, ammonium, nitrites, and phosphate ions were exceeded in the waters of the Akhuryan River from 2013 to 2024. As the Akhuryan River flows through the cities of Amasya and Shirak, its water quality deteriorates. This is due to the discharge of untreated or inadequately treated domestic wastewater from these cities, as well as unorganized runoff from fields. In 2013 and 2014, water quality at sampling point No. 36 of the Ashotsk River upstream of Artashen was "excellent" (class 1), while in other years it was "good" (class 2). In 2013 and 2014, water quality at sampling point No. 37 at the mouth of the Ashotsk River was "good" (class 2). In 2022 and 2024, water quality was unsatisfactory for arsenic and boron levels. In the remaining years, water quality at the mouth of the Karkachun River was assessed as "average" (class 3) for iron, arsenic, and boron, suspended solids, dissolved oxygen, chemical DO, COD and BOD₅. Throughout the study period, water quality at the mouth of the Karkachun River was assessed as "poor" (class 5), primarily due to suspended solids, DO, COD, BOD₅, ammonium, nitrite, and phosphate ions, as well as manganese.

Water quality in the Metsamor River was generally satisfactory to unsatisfactory at all monitoring points. From 2013 to 2024, exceedances of standards were observed for manganese, iron, boron, arsenic, suspended solids, DO, COD and ammonium, nitrite, and phosphate ions.

The analysis of the obtained data can be used for complex management of water resource quality assessment in communities.

References

1. Sargsyan V.O. Waters of Armenia. *Yerevan: EGYAC. 2008. 208 p.(in Rusiam)*
2. Simonyan G. (2021) Systemic-entropic Approach for Assessing Water Quality of Rivers, Reservoirs, and Lakes Inland Waters — *Dynamics and Ecology / Ed. by A. Devlin, J. Pan, M.M. Shah/. London: Intech Open, 2, pp 19–39. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.72894.*
3. Pirumyan G.P., Simonyan G.S, Margaryan L.A. Geocological Evaluational Integrating Index of Natural Waters and other Systems. *Yerevan: Copy Print LTD. 2019 244 . DOI: 10.18411/Assessment-of-Natural-Water-Simonyan-2019*
4. List of fishery standards, maximum permissible concentrations (MPCs), and estimated safe exposure levels (ESELs) of harmful substances for water bodies of fishery importance. *M; VNIRO, 1999 304p. (in Russian)*
5. Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. *Official Journal of the European Communities. 2000. 48. 1–73.*
6. Water quality in the Danube River Basin. International Comunicions for the Danube River, *TNMN. Yerbook. 2005.38 p.*
7. The RA Government Decree №75-N of 27 March 2011 "On the Establishment of Water Quality Standards for Each Water Basin Management Area Depending on the Territory Peculiarities" <https://www.arlis.am/hy/acts/65705> (in Arnenian)
8. Simonyan G.S. Analysis of the Ecological State of Rivers of the Ararat Water Basin Management Area Using Background Concentrations. *Studies in Science of Science,2025, Vol. 43, No 9, 158–163. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17263922*
9. Simonyan G.S. Analysis of the Ecological State of the Agstev and Getik Rivers using Background Concentrations. *Science of Law,2025, No 4, 60-63. DOI: 10.55284/355y3z02*
10. Simonyan G.S., Simonyan A.G., Pirumyan G.P. Systemic-Entropy Approach for Estimating the Water Quality of a River. *Oxid Commun;*2018, 41 (2); 307-217.
11. On the results of ecological monitoring of the environment of the Republic of Armenia. Bulletin. 2013-2024. Hydrometeorological Monitoring Center. Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Armenia. [URL:http://www.armmonitoring.am/publications/cat/16?type=monthly](http://www.armmonitoring.am/publications/cat/16?type=monthly)